

WAVERAM

Closed Cycle Power Take Off for OWC Wave Energy Devices

WP3-D2: Functional Specification of PTO Valves

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PREFACE

This document is in part of ongoing research by Waveram & TCD in the development of an appropriate Power-Take off system for the application of wave energy converters (WECs), under the SEAI National Energy Research Development and Demonstration Funding Programme. This document details the process of determining the functional specifications of the non-return valves required within the Waveram PTO. This work builds on work conducted within work packages 1 and 2.

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1 Introduction

In contrast to a typical floating-point absorber with a bi-directional oscillatory air-flow at the PTO, an advantage of the Waveram, is that it will exhibit relatively consistent uni-directional flow at the turbine allowing for much more efficient power conversion. To achieve this, two key additional components are required; an air accumulator and non-return valves (NRVs). While the accumulator is a simple enclosed area, the NRVs are a much more complex component.

The role of the NRV is to force the air to enter and leave the central pumping chamber through separate ducts allowing for a pressure differential to accumulate across the PTO. They are a critical component to the Waveram operating principle and thus can significantly impact the overall device performance if not designed to the correct specifications. Before a detailed design of this subcomponent can begin, it is important that the exact requirements of the NRVs are understood and their influence on the system analysed.

This report summarises the analysis conducted of the non-return valves using the validated numerical model before proposing potential solutions for the component. Sections 2 & 3 overview the role of the NRV within the device and its implementation in the numerical model. Section 4 summarises the sensitivity analyses conducted in order to determine the appropriate sizing and desired characteristics of the component. This information is then be used to establish minimum requirements and inform the initial design suggestion detailed in sections 5 and 6.

2 Application in Device

A non-return valve or check valve, is a component that only allows fluid flow in a singular direction. The most common implementation are self-actuated as they are controlled by the fluid flow itself. Depending on the application, there are many possible types including swing, ball, spring or diaphragm based.

The NRV is a critical component for the Waveram PTO. Two sets are required as depicted in figure 1. Firstly, connecting the pumping chamber to the pressure accumulator (1.) and secondly, connecting the pumping chamber to the low-pressure accumulator / external atmosphere (3.)

The NRVs must only allow airflow in a singular direction when a positive pressure differential exists. This will allow for the pumping chamber to push compressed air through to the high-pressure accumulator during the compression stroke while ensuring air does not leak back from the accumulator during the expansion stroke. The inlet valve, is faced in the opposite direction, allowing for air intake to the pumping chamber during the expansion stroke while not losing compressed air to this side during the compression stroke¹.

Another solution for the Waveram PTO is to use actuated valves with an active control system, which opens and closes with system command. Correctly implemented, electronically operated valves will have no opening resistance, are more robust but require additional electronics & control.

Figure 1: Simplified schematic of the Waveram PTO.

¹ Previous studies have investigated the influence of replacing the in-flow NRV (3.) with a controlled two-way valve, equalizing the pressure between the atmosphere and pumping chamber as soon as the compression stroke ends. However, this was found to not be beneficial to the system performance. Breaking the 'air-spring' effect in the expansion stroke vents stored energy from the pumping chamber, reducing the overall relative motions.

3 Implementation in Numerical Model

In order to represent the NRV system within the numerical model, assumptions must be made about their behaviour. If we assume, that once opened, the valve behaves much like an orifice plate with an opening area $C_v A_v$ and a damping coefficient $k_v = \frac{\rho}{2(C_v A_v)^2}$, we can derive the following equations to represent the mass flow as a function of time.

$$q_1(t) = \begin{cases} C_{V,1} A_{V,1} \sqrt{2\rho_{PC}} \sqrt{P_{PC} - P_{HP} - P_{opening}} & \text{for } P_{PC} - P_{HP} > P_{opening} \\ 0 & \text{for } P_{PC} - P_{HP} < P_{opening} \end{cases} \quad (\text{kg/s})$$

$$q_3(t) = \begin{cases} C_{V,3} A_{V,3} \sqrt{2\rho_{atm}} \sqrt{P_{atm} - P_{PC} - P_{opening}} & \text{for } P_{atm} - P_{PC} > P_{opening} \\ 0 & \text{for } P_{atm} - P_{PC} < P_{opening} \end{cases} \quad (\text{kg/s})$$

Variables $q_1(t)$ and $q_3(t)$ are the instantaneous mass flow rates. The system pressures, P_{PC} , P_{HP} and densities, ρ_{PC} are required inputs for the calculation. The multiple $C_V A_V$ represents the effective combined opening area of each valve set where A_V = valve area in m^2 and C_V represents the valve flow coefficient which is assumed to be a fixed multiple in the initial analysis. Although this represents a simplistic representation of the valve behaviour, it provides a good tool for sizing and sensitivity studies.

This study of the NRVs is conducted with a validated time-domain numerical model of the Waveram device [1].

4 Sensitivity Analysis

Before determining the most suitable valve for the WaveRam PTO, it is important to first understand the valve performance requirements, the trade-offs involved, and the influence each parameter has on the overall system performance.

This section highlights the results from a number of sensitivity analyses conducted regarding the characteristics of the non-return valves. For the purpose of this report three sea states are considered to provide an insight in realistic conditions across the wave spectrum. The scale and site in question is a ¼ scale Waveram device for deployment at the Biscay Marine Energy Platform (BiMEP) maintaining consistency with all other deliverables within the SEAI RD&D funding programme.

The sea states highlighted in this report are;

- (a) $H_s = 2.75m, T_p = 13s$ - Middle of energy scatter
- (b) $H_s = 4.75m, T_p = 12.5s$ - Near operating limit & resonance.
- (c) $H_s = 1.25m, T_p = 9.5s$ - Centre of occurrences

Each valve characteristic is considered in isolation despite the fact that in reality, they will not necessarily be independent of each other. For example, selecting a larger valve area will likely require a larger cracking pressure.

4.1 Valve Size

Each set of NRVs must have a large enough opening area so as to not to significantly restrict airflow. However, a larger valve system will result in increased costs while it is also clear that there exists limited space within the pumping chamber. Using the equations in section 3, a sensitivity analysis was conducted on the valve effective area, $C_V A_V$.

As anticipated, it was determined that for optimal performance, a larger valve is required for more energetic sea states. Figure [2] indicates that minimal improvement in performance is observed for an effective area above 0.15m^2 for all sample sea states. In order to ensure optimal performance across the entire spectrum, the valve should be large enough as to not infringe on performance of the most energetic yet operational sea states.

Assuming a discharge coefficient $C_V = 0.63$, which was determined as the average for the orifices during the EuropeWave tank-testing campaign [1], an effective area of $C_V A_V = 0.15\text{m}^2$ corresponds to a valve open area of $A_V = 0.24\text{m}^2$ for both the inlet and outlet flow valve separately. This is a significant size to be incorporated at the top of the pumping chamber.

Figure 2: Sensitivity analysis - NRV area.

4.2 Cracking Pressure

An idealized non-return valve set would have zero opening resistance $P_{opening} = 0 Pa$, thus allowing for maximum airflow in the desired direction, and in turn, increasing power at the PTO. However, in reality, a positive pressure differential is required in order to open the mechanism that creates the seal.

Figure [3] shows how maximising system performance requires minimizing the valve cracking pressure. In order to inform the upcoming valve design stages, it is also important to understand how exactly the valve opening pressure impacts performance. Studies using the numerical model indicate a relatively steady loss in performance with increasing valve opening pressure. Performance loss during less energetic sea states will be proportionally greater for the same increase in the cracking pressure.

Figure 3: Sensitivity analysis - Opening pressure

4.3 Response Time

While it is likely that the Waveram will utilize self-actuating valves, consideration is also being given to mechanical operation requiring a motor and electronic control system. A controlled valve will have a response or reaction time between the sending of the electrical signal and the valve becoming fully open. In order to maintain a negligible effect on the overall performance of the Waveram, the actuation time should not exceed 0.15s. While this is certainly ample time for electrical signals, depending on the opening mechanism or valve size, a mechanically operated flap or butterfly valve may need to be designed such that it can go from fully open to fully closed and vice versa within this time frame.

Figure 4: Sensitivity analysis - Actuation time

4.4 Sealing Pressure

If the NRV is fabricated from rubber or flexible material a sufficient back pressure may be required in order to create a seal. Alternatively, this behaviour could develop with wear and tear. Figure 5 show the influence of the sealing pressure on the overall device performance. This study assumes that on average, the NRV is able to restrict flow in the reverse direction by an average of 75% up until its sealing pressure. Above which, it is then able to prevent 100% of air flow. While this is a very simplified representation of a NRV in operation, it provides a good indication of the sensitivity of performance to this characteristic.

Figure 5: Sensitivity analysis - Sealing pressure

5 Valve Specifications

From the various studies and analysis conducted to date, the following NRV specifications have been determined for a ¼ scale Waveram device deployable at BiMEP test site;

- Effective opening area of $C_V A_V = 0.15 \text{ m}^2$.
- A minimized cracking pressure, (1kPa maximum).
- Minimised response time, (0.15s maximum).
- Rated for back-pressures up to 4 bar.
- Suitable in a marine environment. (Air + Seawater mixture).
- Be able to operate on a constantly moving, rolling and pitching device.

No precise specification is made with respect to the sealing pressure as the results obtained from simulation depend significantly on the assumptions made regarding the valve design. However, it is also clear that this should be minimized.

The determined specifications are very different to common off-the-shelf components mainly used for air tools or air compressors. These components are usually designed with small diameters (5 – 20mm) for pressures up to 10bar or greater [2]. The Waveram will require a custom design for the very different application.

6 Potential Concepts

During recent scaled prototype testing of the Waveram device at the FloWave research facility, flap valves formed from rubber were implemented and proved effective at providing little resistance to airflow in the desired direction while creating a sufficient seal in the opposite direction. Images of this valve are shown in figure 6. Figure 7 shows a potential scaling method for this type of valve. Benefits of a repeating array include;

- Maintaining a low opening resistance
- Scalable pattern
- Progressive failure with slow decline in performance vs single point failure
- Easier maintenance when replacing single modules.

However further assessment for the rubber flap valve is required for;

- Suitability at larger pressures and flow rates
- Sealing ability over time – fatigue life as material wears.
- Impact on performance as one or more flap fails.
- Influence of pitch/roll on valve sealing ability.
- Influence of proximity to sea water

This is a relatively simple configuration for an NRV that worked well on a short time span in a controlled lab environment. Further research is required to determine the suitability of this configuration in a marine environment.

Figure 6: NRV set during prototype testing of the Waveram device at the FloWave research facility, April 2022.[1]

Figure 7: NRV array configuration - Proposed scaling method for the tested flap-valve. [3]

An alternative configuration consists of a rigid vertical flap-valve such as that depicted in figure 8. A valve in this configuration would need to be weighted, such as in the image, spring loaded at the joint or mechanically controlled. Similarly, to a rubber valve, the optimal configuration will likely include a modular design with multiple smaller valves providing the same benefits as listed previously. The potential benefits of a mechanical control system over a weighted or spring-loaded mechanism are;

- No opening resistance when correctly implemented
- Notice of failure
- Wider opening area and thus reduced surface area required.

However, with this comes increased complexity & cost due to the on-board electrical system required. While an array setup is feasible, it will likely not be able to consist of such a large quantity as depicted in figure 7.

Figure 6: Potential NRV configuration: Weighted rigid vertical flap.

7 Placement within device assembly

The NRV's will be placed at the top of the pumping chamber, likely within an area of 'fixed volume' which during normal operation, will not be exposed to the internal water level or significant splashing. The location of the outlet valve within the assembly is depicted in figure 10.

Figure 8: Proposed Waveram assembly with allocated NRV area within fixed volume above pumping chamber. [3]

Figure 7: Air path through system [3]

8 Conclusion & Future Work

In this report the basic requirements of the NRV valves are evaluated using validated numerical modelling. For the demonstrator ¼ scale Waveram considered in this research, an effective area of 0.15 m^2 is required for each set to facilitate the expected airflows. Due to the time length of the PTO compression-expansion cycle, the response time is not expected to be a limiting factor. Provided it is below 0.15s, a faster response will have no discernible influence. However, analysis does show that performance will significantly reduce with a larger opening resistance or back-leak. The sensitivity studies conducted in this report were done so in isolation of other performance characteristics and thus will need to be revisited during the more detailed design phase.

A potential valve configuration and the placement within the assembly is also discussed in this report however, further design and testing is required in order to assess suitability within a realistic marine environment. The next objectives of Waveram Ltd is to now focus on the design and testing of several PTO components in a relevant environment, of which the NRVs are a significant component. The work presented in this report will provide useful information for the non-return valve design in the next phase.

9 References

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